

PAST SIMPLE TENSE-DEFINITION, STRUCTURE, RULES, USES AND EXAMPLES

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Abstract: This academic paper has 16 tenses in English, and one of them is the past simple tense. Also, this tense is explained with a wide range of examples.

Keywords: past simple, represent, action, structure, rules.

Introduction: The Simple Past Tense

The simple past tense, in English, is used to represent an action/event that took place in the past. With many verbs, the simple past tense is formed by adding an 'ed' or a 'd' to the end of the base verb. However, there are other verbs which behave differently and take different spellings when used in the simple past form.

Definition of Simple Past Tense

The 'simple past tense', according to the Cambridge Dictionary, is defined as "the form of a verb used to describe an action that happened before the present time and is no longer happening. It is usually made by adding -ed." The Collins Dictionary defines the 'simple past tense' as "a tense used to refer to the past." The Macmillan Dictionary defines the simple past tense as "the tense used to talk about habitual actions, behaviour, or situations that happened or existed before now."

Structure of the Simple Past Tense

Learning the structure of the simple past tense can be made simple if you analyse how the tense is used in the positive, negative, interrogative and negative interrogative formats. Look at the table below to have a better understanding of the same.

The main part: Rules and Points to Remember When Using the Simple Past Tense
When conjugating a verb in the simple past tense, there are a few points you have to bear in mind.

Conjugating regular verbs – In order to present the main verb in the sentence, you just have to add '-ed' to the end of the regular verb and '-d' to the end of a regular verb which ends with an 'e'.

For example: Reach – reached, kick – kicked, walk – walked, confess – confessed,
work –

worked

Like – liked, introduce – introduced, force – forced, announce – announced,

` notice – noticed

Verbs that remain the same – Some verbs take the same spelling as the base verb and remain the same in the past tense.

For example: Cut – cut, put – put, hurt – hurt, set – set, hit – hit

Verbs that take different spelling patterns – Irregular verbs are seen to follow different spelling patterns and there is no rule as such to explain why they are so.

For example: Buy – bought, think – thought, draw – drew, drink – drank, see – saw

What Do You Use the Simple Past Tense For?

The simple past tense can be used to,

Refer to an action or event that happened in the past

Speak about something that was true for some time in the past

Explain something that happened more than once in the past

Forming the Simple Past Tense – Examples

To help you understand how the simple past tense can be used, here are a few examples.

Referring to an action that happened in the past

We went to the park yesterday evening.

I totally forgot about the meeting.

Manu opened the door for the guests.

How to make the simple past negative

Fortunately, there is a formula for making simple past verbs negative, and it's the same for both regular and irregular verbs (except for the verb to be). The formula is did not + [root form of verb]. You can also use the contraction didn't instead of did not.

Wolfgang did not brag too much about his hula hoop skills.

Wolfgang's girlfriend didn't see the contest.

For the verb to be, you don't need the auxiliary did. When the subject of the sentence is singular, use was not or wasn't. When the subject is plural, use were not or weren't.

Conclusion.

The past simple is usually formed by adding d, ed, or ied to the base form of the verb, however, in English there are many irregular verbs that take on a completely different form in the past tense. Some people call this the V2 form of the verb. The best thing to do is to try and memorize them.

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